

Opportunities after Covid in vegetables marketing

Vinod Hanumant Awaghade

Assistant Professor, Yashwantrao Chavan Mahavidyalaya, Pachwad. Department of Commerce
Shivaji University Kolhapur
Maharashtra

Email-vinodawaghade86@gmail.com

Abstract-

India is an agricultural country. Farmers in India mainly give priority to agriculture. Every farmer supports his family from the income from agriculture. Especially after the corona epidemic, leafy vegetables have become very important. A diet of leafy vegetables is very important for every person to have a good life. Farmers get a good income from the production of leafy vegetables, fruit vegetables and tuber vegetables. After covid, many opportunities are seen for the leafy vegetable business. Every person in the society, from children to the elderly, consumes leafy vegetables in their diet. Our country has a tradition of agriculture. Farmers grow a variety of crops. Farmers mainly focus on the production of leafy vegetables and fruits. This agricultural product provides cash to the farmers. The farmer is the king of all of us in the country. Only if the farmer survives can the country run smoothly. The farmer works hard to produce leafy vegetables and fruits and vegetables. Many factors in society depend on agricultural production. Agriculture generates a lot of employment. All agricultural products come in essential services. This means that you need vegetables every day. That is why the researcher has chosen to research this subject. Farmers can get higher yields in agriculture if they get good online tools.

Introduction -

India is an agricultural country. Farmers in India mainly give priority to agriculture. Every farmer supports his family from the income from agriculture. Especially after the corona epidemic, leafy vegetables have become very important. A diet of leafy vegetables is very important for every person to have a good life. Farmers get a good income from the production of leafy vegetables, fruit vegetables and tuber vegetables. After covid, many opportunities are seen for the leafy vegetable business. Every person in the society, from children to the elderly, consumes leafy vegetables in their diet. India is an agricultural country. Agriculture is the backbone of our country's economy. Good livelihood can be achieved by selling leafy vegetables, fruits and tubers. Mainly farmers are growing different crops. Changes are made in the production of vegetables as per the market demand. Everyone in the society is a consumer of agricultural products. If enough water is available, farmers can produce better. Farmers are determined to overcome any challenge.

Keywords- e-commerce, e-banking etc.

Objectives-

1. To study the concept of vegetables.
2. To study the types of vegetables.
3. To study the Importance of vegetables marketing.
4. To study the opportunities in vegetables marketing.

Research Methodology- The present study is based on secondary source of data . secondary

data is collected through various books , Journals, Websites and Internet. For the collection of primary data the researcher has paid visit to market committees (Secretary) ,farmers and agents .It is after having detailed discussion the present data is collected.

Data collection:

1. Primary Data:

For the collection of primary data the researcher has paid visit to market committees (Secretary), farmers and agent's .It is after having detailed discussion the present data is collected.

2. Secondary Data:

The secondary data is derived from the following sources:

1. Books
2. Magazines
3. Journals
4. News paper

Concept- The word vegetable refers the dictionary meaning, a plant or part of plant which is eaten as food.

Types of vegetables -

- a) **Leafy vegetable** - broad beans, spinach, Fenugreek, Dill leaves, Safflower, cluster beans, bell paper etc.
- b) **A root vegetable** - a potato, carrot, Sweet potato, onion, Garlic, ginger etc.
- c) **A fruit vegetable-** Bringel, Green peas, flower, Tomato, Pumpkin, Drum sticks, Ribbed gourd , Capsicum, Green chilies, Cabbage etc.

(Oxford advanced learners dictionary, Jonathan couter oxford university press 1995)

Marketing Concept: Marketing doesn't mean only buying and purchasing the things. The concept has a broad meaning. It deal with the needs of the people, consumer, marketing is to satisfy human the needs. Whenever a consumer goes to markets, he seeks the advantage behind the product. It can be well explained with the example. When a consumer wants to buy a facial cream, he doesn't need only a cream at all, he wants a fairness that's why he tends to buy a cream. Thus marketing doesn't remain in that limited contextual background. Traditional market was a physical place where buyers and sellers together exchange goods.

Importance of leafy vegetables:

1. **Leafy vegetables provide vitamins-** Consuming leafy vegetables in daily diet helps to get a lot of vitamins. The vitamin reduces the incidence of illness. From very young children to the elderly, everyone consumes leafy vegetables to help them stay healthy.
2. **Eating leafy vegetables improves health-** Consuming green vegetables in daily diet helps in improving health. Leafy vegetables contribute a lot to increase immunity in the body. In the current scenario, there is a huge demand for organic leafy vegetables and fruits.
3. **Suitable for dieting-**Mainly people who want to balance their body weight do diet. Leafy vegetables and fruit vegetables are consumed for diet. Leafy vegetables are important in every person's diet. Eating leafy greens helps boost your immunity. Doctors advise many people to eat leafy vegetables.
4. **Cash and Carry transaction-** Sale of leafy vegetables and fruit vegetables helps the farmers to get cash from daily transactions. The daily income from the sale of leafy vegetables helps a lot to support the family. Selling fruits and vegetables, mainly leafy vegetables, is considered a major source of livelihood.

Opportunities in vegetables marketing:

1. Buying and selling of leafy vegetables, fruits and agricultural products is highly profitable. This method of buying and selling is considered to be very important mainly for subsistence.
2. Leafy vegetables, fruits and all agricultural products come in essential services. There is no other option. Which means it's about to be the most delusional time of the year, as well.

3. Everyone in the community is a consumer of this product. Taking good products using organic fertilizers will create an opportunity to make good profits.
4. Vegetables are considered to be a very important part of the daily diet. There is a lot of demand for these products every day.
5. Good products make you dominant in the market. Quality products create opportunities to export agricultural products.
6. Collective farming by farmers will enable them to supply to the consumers as per their demand. The product can be supplied in less time, at lower cost.
7. There will be a lot of opportunities for agriculture in the future. Good demand for the product and good quality of the product will make it possible to get a definite advantage.
8. It will be possible to easily compete if the products are manufactured according to the changing market conditions.
9. Currently, chemical-free agricultural products are in high demand. It will be possible to get more benefits if all the people cultivate collectively.
10. It is possible to buy vegetable products with very little capital. That is, it is possible to make a profit in the least amount of capital.

Conclusions-

The purchase and sale of leafy vegetables, fruits and agricultural products has the potential for maximum financial gain. There are going to be a lot of opportunities in this farming sector in the future. It is possible to survive in the competition by farming with the help of new modern tools. It is important to make the right decision considering the market opportunities and demand. Agriculture is playing an important role in the development of our country. Agriculture definitely benefits from employment, imports, exports and the right investment. There is a risk in buying and selling leafy vegetables but there is also a definite benefit. The right decision ability is needed.

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